

At the next stage, the fatty acid is separated from the water by pouring it into a separating funnel and is washed 3 times in hot water and evaporated at 90-95°C for one hour. Synthesized vegetable fatty acid is subjected to infrared spectroscopy analysis and absorption bands are determined. The physico-chemical properties of the obtained fatty acid are analyzed. The synthesized fatty acid is homogenized with ground stone powder and poured into a chemical beaker filled with distilled water and the homogenous mixture is spread over it. Hydrophobicity is checked by keeping it quiet for a day.

To examine the surface activity of the powder, the beaker is moved back and forth for 1 second and repeated 10 times. If the stone dust did not settle to the bottom of the water after the process or did not cloud the water, this indicates that its hydrophilicity has decreased to a minimum, that is, its hydrophobicity has increased. Laboratory studies of a homogeneous mixture of acid and stone powder show that the activated

stone powder remains on the water surface for more than 10 days and does not sink to the bottom of the water and does not cloud the water. As a result, the application of activated stone dust in asphalt pavement increases its service life due to the increase of surface activity.

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STUDY OF PENTYL BROMIDE COMPLEX OF AMIDOAMINE OF SUNFLOWER ACIDS AS A CORROSION INHIBITOR

**Abbasov V.M.,
Agamaliyeva D.B.,
Gurbanova F.J.,
Talybov A.H.,
Efendiyeva L.M.,
Ayyubov I.H.,
Kahramanova K.A.,
Seidzade R.Kh.**

*Institute of Petrochemical Processes named after acad. Y.H. Mammadaliyev
AZ 1025, Baku, Khojaly Ave. thirty;*

Abstract

The protection of metal-containing equipment from corrosion is one of the urgent problems in today's rapidly developing technological environment. This problem is more related to CO₂ corrosion of steel equipment and pipelines in the production and processing of oil and gas, which is the basis of the oil sector [1,2]. Although the corrosion process cannot be completely prevented, there are various ways to significantly reduce its rate. The most effective and easy to use is the use of corrosion inhibitors. [3-6]

Keywords: CO₂ corrosion, inhibitors, amidoamine, triethylenetetraamine, sunflower oil acids

For this purpose, an amidoamine based on sunflower oil acids and triethylenetetraamine was synthesized. In the next step, an inorganic complex of the resulting amide (N-6) is synthesized. using pentyl bromide (C₅H₁₁Br) as alkyl halides. The reaction is preferably carried out in a molar ratio of 1:1, with stirring at 80-81°C for 3 hours. The resulting complex is dark yellow, viscous, readily soluble in isopropyl alcohol. The yield of the complex obtained as a result of the

reaction is 95%. The structure of the resulting complex was confirmed by IR spectroscopy.

The effect of the complex on the kinetics of corrosion of steel in 1% NaCl solution in water saturated with CO₂ on steel surfaces was carried out on the potentiometer "ACM Instruments GILL AC no-1197" at a temperature of 50°C, a pressure of 0.9 bar, for 20 hours. A graphical representation of the results obtained is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Kinetic effect of the complex obtained on the basis of amidoamine of triethylenetetraamine and sunflower oil acids and pentylbromide $C_5H_{11}Br$ (N-6) on CO_2 corrosion

As can be seen from the graph, N-6 at 50 ppm for 20 hours showed an inhibitory effect of 99.7%, reducing the corrosion rate from $\rho=4.15$ mm/yr to $\rho=0.2$ mm/yr. Thus, the synthesized inorganic anionic complex completely protects the steel from CO_2 corrosion.

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